

Inclusion, tolerance and dialogue in mathematics classes

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This paper presents a reflection related to the concepts of inclusion and tolerance in mathematics classes where the differences amongst the students are acknowledged. In a context permeated by tensions, the complexity of teaching and learning processes becomes more evident to try promoting education for all. In order to contribute to a better understanding of practices based on the concept of equity, this paper discusses aspects relating to inclusion, tolerance, and dialogue. Teaching and learning practices based on dialogue can contribute to the fight against oppressive practices, thus favouring tolerance, cooperation, and construction of equity, essentials elements for the inclusion of any student in mathematics classes.

Introduction

This article presents a reflection related to the concepts of inclusion and tolerance in mathematics classes where differences between students are recognized, highlighting aspects that contribute to teaching and learning mathematics guided by the concept of equity.

In the field of education, inclusion can be understood as a commitment to favor under-represented groups in society, people without possibilities for development in schools as it traditionally presents themselves. In this sense, inclusive education is related to ideas of equity and social justice.

Equity differs from equality, recognizing the different means and conditions for distinct groups or people to have access to the same rights. Promote equal access to resources, qualified teachers, and pedagogical support for all students, regardless of their differences, are actions that may be understood as ways to guarantee the same opportunities, but that is not true.

Students from different social groups, with different skills, needs and backgrounds, do not have the same conditions of access to the same rights. For example, a deaf student who uses sign language, in a class without the presence of an interpreter of sign language, will certainly be harmed. Thus, support is necessary for this student to have the same conditions as his colleagues.

Ladson-Billings (2009) also argues that, when using the term equality to refer to learning opportunities, the history of different cultural groups and the ways in which the organization of society has influenced the opportunities offered are neglected to different groups of people. Thus, it emphasizes the importance of recognizing and valuing differences when dealing with issues concerning the chances for all students to be able to achieve academic success.

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Equity includes the recognition of inequities present in society and at school, from different cultures, different social groups, different skills, and the different knowledge that students bring to the classroom (Faustino, 2018). Thus, it assumes that different opportunities need to be created so that different people have access to the same right.

Silva et al (2017) state that in order to promote equity, it is important to ensure the quality of education, enabling students to access and stay in school, as well as the development of citizenship and critical knowledge. The authors argue that issues of social justice, social inequalities, as well as socioeconomic disparities, should relate to equity promoting practices.

Regarding to mathematics education, some authors emphasize the potential of mathematics education in identifying inequities present in society and in establishing a pillar for strengthening struggles for social justice. Struggles for all human beings, regardless of social class, race, gender, ability, religion, need to have access to the same rights. (Frankenstein, 1983; Gutstein, 2006; Skovsmose, 2012)

In research in Mathematics Education the term equity has been mostly related to inclusion, since in societies the cultural diversity is increasing, it is necessary to incorporate including practices that enable students to learn independently of pre-established standards (Bishop, Tan, & Barkatsas, 2015).

The reflections proposed in this article are supported by concerns related to education and social justice with a focus on teaching and learning mathematics in school environments. The discussions presented are based in the experience of inclusive education in Brazilian schools. We defend the idea that an education based on concepts of equity and tolerance can be favored by an approach that favors dialogical communication.

In what follows we present the theoretical perspective related to the concepts of inclusion and tolerance. Then, we present a discussion of aspects related to the dialogue that favored equity in mathematics classes. We conclude by highlighting the importance of dialogical interaction for the practice of tolerance, as well as for the cooperation and construction of equity in educational practices.

An inclusion perspective

Based on conceptions related to human rights, including education progresses with an ideal of equity and presupposes an education centered on the student and their skills and that fully meets their educational needs so that everyone can learn.

This perspective is aimed at all students, nonetheless benefits mainly the students that had been historically excluded or on the margins of the society such as, for example, blacks, elderly, disability and LGBTQ¹ people, as well as, all people who do not have the same education opportunities as the majority of the population.

In Brazil, most of the concerns of inclusive education are related to schooling for people with disabilities due to the historic exclusion suffered by this group during a long period and the fight for access and democratization of education. Since 2008, the introduction of new educational polices related to inclusive education guarantee the access of students with disabilities in regular schools. Thus, the current discussion is directing to permanence of

¹ LGBTQ is an acronym for lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, and queer people.

these students, as well as, students from other underrepresented groups. The reflections presented in this paper are directing to this context.

The presence of students with disabilities in regular schools opens space for questions, positions, doubts, discussions and reconstruction of practices that have not contributed to the inclusion process, as well as to the development of concepts and actions compatible with the school's inclusive proposal. Uncertainties arise since, although there are attractive things related to the inclusion process, there are also problematic aspects.

Apparently, it is a praiseworthy thing to work for inclusion in an educational domain. There does not seem to be any need of justifying an inclusive education. It seems by itself an attractive thing to do. The question is just how to do it. The point to be stressed here, however, is that inclusion is also a contested concept. (Figueiras, Healy, & Skovsmose, 2016, p. 16)

These authors see the word inclusion as a contested concept. That is a concept that can have different modes of interpretation, as well as operate in different discourses. Since it has no defined meanings, it can represent social, economic, religious, political, and cultural controversies. Thus, they believe that one of the ways to explore the contested nature of inclusive education is through the notion of deficiencialism.

Marcone (2015) calls deficiencialism the expression that refers to the construction of disability in terms of standards of normality. To reinforce the disability argument as an invention with an ideal of normality as a parameter, the author sought to view disability as an experience, something that we are subject to and not a previously established condition.

To try to answer some of the questions that moved him, Marcone (2015) sought inspiration in anti-colonial readings and in post-colonial theories, which discusses the ways in which relations between Western countries and their eastern colonies were established. Based on these conceptions, Marcone defined deficiencialism. For the author, disability is something invented by a group that sees itself as normal and puts the group of people with disability like a distinct of them, causing tension throughout an idea of dichotomy, disguised by politically correct speeches.

In general, deficiencialism refers to some groups as disabled and provides opinions on what this group is and is not capable of doing. This is a conception frequently identified in mathematics teaching practices aimed at students with disabilities and confronting such a conception requires a change in the understanding of disabilities.

In this sense, Skovsmose (2019), suggests seeing the term disability throughout the notion of difference, and thus, one can interpret inclusive education as education based on differences. For the author, differences define one of the main characteristics of the human condition and are seen in all spheres of life.

To consider such a conception is to consider the construction of education that supports the learning of all students. Thus, a curriculum designed with the blind student's skills in mind, for example, is still suitable for students with perfect vision. That is, it is possible to think in a school of differences.

Thus, inclusive education can be considered as an education that seeks value differences and not an education that tries to include the different in some standard of normality. For Skovsmose (2019), this conception allows us to interpret inclusive education as new ways of providing a meeting amongst differences.

Tolerance in the meeting amongst differences

Moura (2020) understands encounter as a human ability to be with the other (or others) experiencing a collaborative relationship, which suggests movement, action to discover, to be aware of new things. The author stresses that this relationship is not always possible, since even sharing the same physical space, it is common for people to be at different levels of understanding and abilities. In this sense, the meetings become responsible for promoting a collaborative relationship in living with each other. One of the ways to build such a relationship is through the practice of tolerance.

Falo da tolerância como virtude da convivência humana. Falo, por isso mesmo, da qualidade básica a ser forjada por nós e aprendida pela assunção de sua significação ética – qualidade de conviver com o diferente. Com o diferente, não com o inferior (Freire, 2014, p. 25–26)

I speak of tolerance as a virtue of human coexistence. I speak, for this same reason, of the basic quality to be forged by us and learned throughout the assumption of their ethical meaning – the quality of living with the different. With the different, not with the inferior (author's translation)

In Portuguese, the word tolerate is understood in common sense as a synonym for abide in its sense of resisting something painful or standing firm in the face of an uncomfortable situation. Tolerance in this sense is as if the tolerant did a certain favor to the tolerated, forgiving the supposed inferiority of the tolerated in a benevolent way.

It is common that the presence of students with disabilities in regular schools is understood in this way. Working with these students, in general, is considered praiseworthy and worthy of admiration, precisely because of the belief that they lack something. In this perspective, tolerating different students means accepting them in the school space, but not worrying about developing practices that actually include these students in the teaching and learning processes, since allowing them to be present at school is already seen as a great favor.

The concept of coexistence with the different and the acceptance of this is a point to be highlighted in the ideas of Paulo Freire, which is implicit in all his understanding of education. Freire (2014) breaks with the tolerance paradigm as a virtue of superiority when affirming tolerance as a virtue of human coexistence and not of an individual.

In this perspective, tolerance has a mutual commitment developed through coexistence amongst people, based on human relationships. In other words, the person is tolerant not because he or she is superior, but because he or she recognizes in the other person someone who has a condition different from his or hers.

A tolerância genuína, por outro lado, não exige de mim que concorde com aquele ou aquela a quem tolero ou também não me pede que a estime ou o estime. O que a tolerância autêntica demanda de mim é que respeite o diferente, seus sonhos, suas ideias, suas opções, seus gostos, que não o negue só porque é diferente. O que a tolerância legítima termina por ensinar é que, na sua experiência, aprendo com o diferente. (Freire, 2014, p. 26)

Genuine tolerance, on the other hand, does not require me to agree with the one who I tolerate or also do not ask me to estimate him or her. What authentic tolerance demands from me is that I respect the different, their dreams, their ideas, their options, their tastes, that I do not deny it just because he or she is different. What legitimate tolerance ends me up teaching is that, in its experience, I learn from the different. (author's translation)

In other words, tolerating does not mean agreeing with another, but it requires respect for the different to the point that you can learn from them. Thus, tolerance values all knowledge and skills, which enable the construction of new knowledge.

In this way, I realize a collaborative relationship in which tolerance is practiced, as a relationship in which the other is recognized as a different person, with whom I can learn. In this sense, Moura (2020, p. 194) understands meetings as a meeting between two or more people, who recognize the differences from each other and are open to the new learning possibilities that can arise from that meeting.

This meeting does not happen spontaneously and without any setbacks and, like any human relationship, it is full of tensions. For Freire (2014) tension is an essential element for knowledge, and it is creative since it destabilizes positions imposed as rules or “absolute truths”, in addition to stimulating curiosity, questioning relations of power and oppression.

Thus, the meeting between the different invites us to reflect on the absolute positions that do not contribute to us being tolerant, that is so that we are open to learning from each other.

Like Freire (2014), I believe in tensions as something that contributes to knowledge. The history of the education of people with disabilities in Brazil and all the legislation that supports the presence of these students in regular schools today was only possible due to questions about the power relations and oppressions experienced by these students, which made it possible to search for spaces in schools the right to education and other rights that allow their full participation in life in society, like any citizen.

All achievements by students with disabilities in Brazil, in particular their presence in regular schools, have contributed to new questions about education and new practices, especially with regard to forms of teaching and learning.

To think inclusive education in terms of encounters amongst the different is to think of an education that practices tolerance through the recognition and appreciation of the difference of each one and that sees the possibility of learning from the different. Thus, it is necessary that new possibilities regarding the teaching and learning processes of mathematics be discussed.

Among several possibilities, Skovsmose (2019) highlights Landscapes of Investigation as a proposal that invites encounters between differences in mathematics classes. Such a proposal involves the organization of learning environments that favor ways of communication that challenge the exercise paradigm (Skovsmose, 2000). The typical pattern of communication is dialogue understood as a conversation aimed at learning. Through it, each participant has the opportunity to expose their ideas and defend their point of view, in order to collaborate with collective thinking and the creation of new perspectives.

In what follows are present, a discussion on aspects related to the dialogue that favored inclusion and tolerance in mathematics classes.

Dialogue in mathematics classes

Dialogue is understood as fundamental to establish critical perspectives on mathematics and for the cooperative construction of new mathematical ideas. Dialogue is seen as an element that favors a collaborative learning process and opens spaces for epistemic and socio-political criticism (Moura, 2020).

An essential aspect of the dialogue is the promotion of equity in terms of communication, valuing a horizontal relationship between those involved, and is not influenced by the roles or conditions of teachers and students.

Alrø and Skovsmose (2004) emphasize that promoting equity does not imply denying diversity and differences. For the authors, this refers “[...] to ways of dealing with diversity and difference, and the principal concept is fairness. Fairness does not only refer to emotional aspects, it also refers to the way the content matter of the dialogue is dealt with” (p. 124).

In other words, promoting equity includes dealing with differences and that must be understood as a respectful relationship between people who are partners in carrying out a joint action. Thus, the strength of the arguments must be centered on their importance for the investigation carried out and not because this argument comes from a position that has more or less power in a given relationship.

The authors point out that such an approach is not free of risks due to the higher rate of unpredictability. There are uncertainties when you want to know what the other person thinks, even you suspecting something, you are not sure what the answers will be.

Handle with risks can also be related to student’s feelings. For example, they may feel uncomfortable during the investigation process when they have a contested or rejected opinion by others involved. On the other hand, they can feel happy when the shared perspective helps in the investigation. The unpredictability in this context can also mean new possibilities for learning, contributing to autonomy during the process, knowing that it can happen in different ways.

For Milani (2015) “dialogar é estar com o outro, é mover-se em direção ao outro, ao interessar-se pelo o que outro diz” (p. 203). In this movement to go where the other is, the author presents three elements that she considers essential in a dialogical interaction: *active listening*, *estrangement* and *decentring*.

Active listening involves asking questions and giving non-verbal support (watchful eye; body directed at who speak; a facial expression that shows interest; nodding in the affirmative) to the speaker while seeking to understand their perspective.

Estrangement, on the other hand, can occur when there is a difference between ways of thinking, for example when the teacher thinks of a strategy for solving an exercise, and a student presents another strategy completely different and unexpected. Faced with a situation like this, the teacher can choose to ignore it, insisting on their perspective, which can decrease the chances of dialogical interaction. Or, the teacher can consider the situation that causes strangeness, trying to understand how the student is thinking. This action of understanding the other, going to where he is, is understood by Milani (2015) by *decentring*, which is linked to understanding the point of view of the other who speaks.

Alrø and Skovsmose (2004) call attention to the difficulty of valuing dialogical interactions in a traditional mathematics class, based on solving exercises. In this model, classes are guided by the textbook in which the teacher presents some ideas and teaches techniques necessary for solving exercises that are also found in the book. There are no spaces for questioning or justification about the relevance of exercises that, in general, present only one correct answer.

Skovsmose (2000) refers to this model as teaching based on the exercise paradigm and argues that it should be contrasted by an investigative approach. He states that such an approach is one that has the potential for dialogical communication to occur in the classroom and presents the propose of Landscapes of Investigation as a possibility in this perspective.

Investigating according to the purpose of Landscapes of Investigation includes collectivity and collaboration and for that to happen it is necessary that students get involved through an invitation and not as something imposed. The lines of investigation take shape from the exploration of diverse perspectives giving rise to insights into the approach to a problem. However, those involved must be prepared to renounce a perspective, that is to say, to analyze what would happen if it were not maintained, not placing it as something unquestionable.

The teacher is still responsible for planning, mediation, decisions about the appropriate methodologies for the mathematical contents and for assessment strategies. However, when trying to understand the student's perspectives, the teacher is no longer the only one to have something to teach.

During the dialogic interaction, the students are no longer who just learns and the teacher is no longer the one who just teaches. While learning, students also can teach teachers. The teacher's displacement to understand the student's perspectives may contribute to overcoming the vertical relationship between teacher and students (Faustino, 2018).

Thereby, teachers have the opportunity to learn from students and about students. This movement towards overcoming the vertical relationship during classes, allow students to share their perspectives, their differences, their understandings of the world, their skills, and ways of expressing themselves.

When moving to understand the student's perspectives, the teacher opens up to the reframing of ideas and positions, respecting the several ways of learning and paths to be followed. The methodological and assessment strategies start to also consider the student's perspectives and the way they experience the world. This movement is essential for the construction of equity.

Concluding remarks

In order to contribute to a mathematics education that values differences, Skovsmose (2019) proposes that Inclusive Education be thought of as new ways of providing encounters amongst differences. In this sense, these encounters are understood as a human ability to be with the other (or others) experiencing a dialogue relationship, which considers a movement, an action of discovering, an act of being aware of new things.

To think inclusive education in terms of encounters amongst the differences is to think of an education that practices tolerance in its genuine sense, that is, that recognizes and values the difference of each one and that sees the possibility of learning from the different.

The propose of Landscapes of Investigation shows itself as an invitation to encounter differences in mathematics classes and makes room for dialogical interactions to appear. The characteristics present in the dialogical interaction – active listening, estrangement, and

decentring – contribute to the emergence and maintenance of the dialogue and are identified when there is an interest in understanding what the other says.

In this sense, the potential of dialogic interactions is emphasized for a cooperative relationship in which people act at the level of equity, since it allows differences to be respected, through the action of wanting to know what the other means, regardless of who this other is, their skills or position held during an interaction.

Through dialogical interaction, new meetings are facilitated in the classroom. Teachers learn with students and their differences, making this meeting not just a sharing of the same environment, but a movement to see the other, to want to be together favoring the practice of tolerance, as well as cooperation and the construction of equity, essential elements for the inclusion of all students in mathematics classes.

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